

THE IMPACT OF LEARNERS' SOFT SKILLS ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT, SOCIAL ADAPTATION AND CAREER SUCCESS

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ABSTRACT

The modern labor market requires graduates to possess not only professional knowledge and technical competencies but also soft skills such as communication, teamwork, critical thinking, creativity, and emotional intelligence. These skills play a significant role in academic achievement, social adaptation, and career success, making them a priority in the strategic development of education systems. However, in the context of Kazakhstan, there is a lack of empirical research identifying the specific links between soft skills and labor market success. This study aimed to determine the impact of soft skills on academic performance (GPA), social adaptation, and career success among graduates of higher education institutions in Kazakhstan, as well as to identify the key factors predicting income levels. The study involved 80 graduates. Data were collected through a self-developed questionnaire based on a 10-point Likert scale, which measured five core soft skills components (communication, teamwork, creativity, critical thinking, and emotional intelligence), along with GPA, social adaptation, employment status, and income level. Data analysis was performed in Jamovi using Pearson and Spearman correlations and multiple linear regression. Correlation analysis revealed weak and statistically insignificant relationships between soft skills components and GPA or social adaptation ($p > 0.05$). In contrast, statistically significant positive correlations were found between income level, employment status, and soft skills ($r = 0.706$, $p < 0.001$). Multiple regression results showed that the model explained 55.1% of the variance in income level ($R^2 = 0.551$). The main predictors of career success were employment status ($p < 0.001$) and critical thinking skills ($p = 0.024$). These findings highlight the need for higher education institutions to integrate soft skills training—particularly those fostering strategic and analytical thinking—into curricula alongside professional education to better prepare graduates for labor market success. *This research has been/was/is funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Grant No. BR28713097).*

Keywords: soft skills, academic performance, social adaptation, career success, critical thinking.

Introduction

In today's society, the ability to adapt to a changing environment and achieve success has become a crucial attribute, underscoring the importance of soft skills and academic achievement for social adaptation and career success [1]. Career adaptability is a key factor in overcoming professional transitions, involving the adjustment of both the individual and the environment by leveraging psychological and social resources to ensure job satisfaction [2]. Individuals with well-developed soft skills respond effectively to shifting demands, demonstrate readiness to embrace change, and address challenges through innovative solutions [3]. Academic achievement provides a solid foundation of knowledge and critical thinking, equipping individuals with the tools necessary for success in diverse fields, while soft skills enable the effective application of this knowledge in real-life contexts.

Career adaptability is a continuous process shaped by the interaction between the individual and the environment. It allows for maintaining balance during changes in professional roles. Furthermore, academic success provides the foundational knowledge required for a career, and the ability to acquire, adapt, and apply this knowledge is a decisive factor for sustainable success [4]. In today's labor market—characterized by technological advancement and globalization—the ability to acquire new skills, adapt to change, and collaborate effectively with diverse teams is highly valued [5]. The combination of academic achievement and soft skills not only determines employability but also the potential for professional growth, career satisfaction, and long-term success.

The influence of various skills and academic achievement on social adaptation and career success has become a significant research topic in both education and the labor market. Studies show that socio-emo-

tional skills such as flexibility, self-management, innovation, social interaction, and emotional stability help learners adapt to future changes and move confidently toward career goals [6]. Moreover, the close relationship between academic achievement and career planning, self-assessment, and adaptability contributes to students' success in social, professional, and academic environments [7], [8]. Thus, developing soft skills and academic achievement plays a decisive role in ensuring young people's social adaptation and readiness for life and the labor market [9], [10].

However, the existing literature reveals several gaps. First, the conceptual definition of flexible skills (soft skills) varies across sources, and there is no fully standardized approach to their measurement. Second, the relationship between academic achievement and social adaptation is often context-dependent, limiting the generalizability of findings. Therefore, this study aims to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the influence of soft skills and academic achievement on social adaptation and career success, as well as to empirically assess their interrelationship.

Soft skills encompass attributes such as problem-solving, critical thinking, communication, and teamwork, enabling individuals to overcome complex situations and interact effectively with others. These skills are crucial for performing both predictable and unexpected tasks in work and employment contexts [11]. They significantly contribute to the adaptability index, which reflects an individual's capacity to succeed in new or changing environments.

Flexibility as a personal trait signifies readiness to embrace change and becomes a stable characteristic defining an individual's core profile [12]. The ability to adapt to change is highly valued by employers, who seek individuals capable of demonstrating resilience, learning quickly, and contributing effectively in dynamic work settings [13]. Moreover, soft skills enhance social adaptation, enabling individuals to build strong relationships, navigate diverse social contexts, and collaborate effectively with others [14]. People with high levels of soft skills tend to manage interpersonal relationships effectively, resolve conflicts, and foster a sense of belonging within communities.

As a multifaceted construct, flexibility includes cognitive, behavioral, and emotional dimensions and determines the capacity to succeed in varied and complex environments. Additionally, soft skills play a pivotal role in fostering innovation and creativity, enabling individuals to view problems from different perspectives, generate new ideas, and implement effective solutions [15].

Academic achievement forms the foundation of personal and professional development, providing individuals with strong knowledge, skills, and critical thinking abilities. It develops the capacity to understand

complex issues, evaluate evidence, and make informed decisions. Academic success is typically defined as positive outcomes resulting from individuals' career decisions, behaviors, and work experiences [16]. It encompasses not only the mastery of subject knowledge but also the development of cognitive strategies necessary for lifelong learning.

Moreover, academic achievement serves as a "signaling mechanism" in the labor market, influencing employers' perceptions of candidates' competence, diligence, and growth potential [17]. Higher education contributes to career opportunities, improved socioeconomic indicators, and professional advancement. However, its influence extends beyond economic benefits, fostering attributes such as self-efficacy, goal orientation, and resilience, which help individuals overcome career challenges and achieve long-term professional satisfaction.

The synergy between academic achievement and soft skills cannot be overstated. While academic preparation opens doors to professional opportunities, soft skills enable the effective application of knowledge in evolving professional roles and multidisciplinary contexts [18]. In today's knowledge-based economy, success often depends on the combination of cognitive, social, and emotional competencies.

Soft skills and academic achievement complement each other, forming the essential foundation for social adaptation and career success.

Research Methodology

This study aimed to determine the impact of soft skills on academic achievement, social adaptation, and career success within the higher education system. The research design consisted of two main methodological steps: (1) a systematic review of the scientific literature, and (2) an empirical survey followed by statistical data analysis.

Literature Review

The first stage involved a systematic analysis of theoretical and empirical studies related to the research topic. Peer-reviewed articles from the *Scopus* and *Mendeley* databases, as well as proceedings from international conferences, were examined. The selection of literature followed the PRISMA methodological guidelines to ensure comprehensiveness and avoid duplicate data. The review included studies that assessed the relationships between soft skills indicators, GPA, social adaptation, and employment outcomes.

Empirical Research Design

In the empirical stage, a questionnaire (Table 1) based on a Likert scale was developed to collect data. The survey captured information on respondents' core soft skills and career indicators. The evaluation scale ranged from 1 to 10 (1 – very low level, 10 – very high level).

Table 1.

Survey variables			
Variable	Measurement Method	Evaluation Scale	Data Source
Communication	Ability to express ideas clearly, active listening skills	1–10	Survey
Teamwork	Ability to work collaboratively, share responsibilities	1–10	Survey
Creativity	Ability to generate new ideas, solve problems creatively	1–10	Survey
Critical Thinking	Ability to analyze information, make evidence-based decisions	1–10	Survey
Emotional Intelligence	Ability to manage emotions, empathy	1–10	Survey
GPA (Academic Performance)	Grade Point Average	0–4 or 0–100 grading scale	Official academic records
Social Adaptation	Level of adaptation to social environments	1–50	Survey
Employment Status	Employed/Not employed	Dichotomous (0–1)	Self-reported data
Income	Monthly income level	Ordinal scale	Self-reported data

Data Processing and Analysis

The collected data were processed using the *Jamovi* statistical software platform. The analysis included the following stages [17, 18]:

- Incomplete responses and extreme values were removed; the normality of numerical variables was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test;
- Pearson’s and Spearman’s correlation coefficients (depending on data distribution) were calculated to evaluate the relationships between soft skills indicators and GPA;

- Linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the influence of soft skills indicators on social adaptation and career success. Model quality was assessed using R , R^2 , standardized β coefficients, and p -values.

For all statistical tests, a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was applied.

The result of the study

The results of the study look at the relationship between flexible skills and academic achievement in different contexts. The following describes the empirical research carried out on this topic (Table 2).

Table 2.

Description of the studies covered

Study	Research Design	Sample	Skills Measured	Outcomes Assessed	Findings
<i>Mirzoyan et al., 2024</i>	Descriptive correlational study	Management students at Lomonosov Moscow State University (sample size not specified)	Leadership, persuasion, analytical skills, decision-making, communication	Academic grades in 22 subjects, GPA, regression analysis	Positive correlations found between leadership, communication, analytical skills, and GPA/subject grades [19].
<i>Stepanova & Zeer, 2019</i>	Descriptive correlational study	Students (institution not specified)	Communication, motivation, reflection, innovation, stress tolerance	Self-actualization, resilience, ability to act under stress; Spearman correlation	Communication, motivation, and stress tolerance were linked to self-actualization and ability to act under stress [20].
<i>Shehu Lokaj et al., 2021</i>	Cross-sectional survey	200 students (100 from private and 100 from public universities, Kosovo)	15 soft skills (Goldsmith scale)	Soft skills development, job readiness; Kendall’s Tau-b, Mann–Whitney U	Higher soft skills levels were positively associated with students’ job readiness [21].
<i>The Role of Soft Competences, 2024</i>	Cross-sectional survey	60 companies, 150 students (country not specified)	Communication, emotional intelligence, motivation	Professional adaptation, career success	Communication and emotional intelligence were found to influence professional adaptation and career success [22].

<i>Anufrieva, 2023</i>	Mixed-methods study	78 students from Tomsk Polytechnic University (final-year undergraduates, Master's, and PhD students, Russia)	Teamwork, communication, leadership, problem-solving, creativity, critical thinking, decision-making, lifelong learning, motivation, self-control	Prioritization of skills, competence model	Communication, teamwork, motivation, and creativity were identified as key professional competencies [23].
<i>Ladzina, 2023</i>	Mixed-methods with longitudinal elements	78 students (1st and 3rd year, aged 18–27), Amanzholov University (Kazakhstan)	Emotional intelligence (perception, regulation, motivation, empathy), reflection	Competence acquisition, variance analysis, significant differences	Emotional intelligence and reflection were identified as important factors in competence development [24].
<i>Amantaeva et al., 2024</i>	Cross-sectional study	538 students (3rd/4th year), Kostanay Regional University (Kazakhstan)	Not specified	Confidence in employment, statistical analysis in R	Positive relationship found between students' confidence levels and employment opportunities [25].
<i>Kamarova, 2021</i>	Not specified (possibly longitudinal survey)	Company executives in Russia (employer survey)	Not specified	Employer requirements, contribution of soft/hard skills to success	Employers rated soft skills highly in contributing to success [26].
<i>Majid et al., Importance of Soft Skills</i>	Cross-sectional study	188 business students, 4 Singapore universities	Teamwork, decision-making, problem-solving, time management, critical thinking	Importance for social interaction, career, academic achievement	Teamwork, decision-making, and time management skills were found to positively influence academic achievement and career outcomes [27].

The studies presented above examine the influence of students' soft skills on academic achievement, career success, and social adaptation from multiple perspectives. These studies were conducted in Kazakhstan, Russia, and Singapore, and the samples included undergraduate, Master's, and PhD students, as well as employer representatives.

A total of nine studies focused on analyzing the impact of soft skills on social adaptation and career success. Most studies involved higher education students and graduates.

By research design

Four studies used a cross-sectional survey method; Three studies employed a descriptive correlational approach; Two studies applied a mixed-methods design, including longitudinal elements; One study did not specify the research design.

By sample population

Five studies were conducted with undergraduate students; One study included a mixed group of final-year undergraduates, Master's, and PhD students; One study targeted only employers; Another study included both students and employers; Two studies did not provide specific population details.

Skills assessed

The most frequently examined skills were communication and teamwork (in four studies); Leadership,

problem-solving, decision-making, and motivation appeared in three studies; Creativity, critical thinking, and emotional intelligence were examined in two studies; Other skills mentioned only once included reflection, analytical ability, persuasion, stress tolerance, lifelong learning, self-control, adaptability, communicative literacy, public speaking, argumentation, and time management; One study assessed soft skills in aggregate form without differentiating specific skills; Two studies did not specify the exact skills measured.

Outcomes assessed

Four studies examined employment and career success indicators (e.g., job readiness, professional achievement, confidence in employability); Two studies measured academic achievement (GPA, academic performance); Two studies focused on professional adaptation or self-actualization; Two studies explored labor market demands or employer expectations; Another two studies analyzed skill hierarchies or competence models.

Across multiple studies, soft skills such as communication, leadership, decision-making, emotional intelligence, and others were recognized as important factors for employability, professional adaptation, and personal development. In some cases, they were also linked to academic performance, but their strongest documented influence was on career success and em-

ployment confidence. However, in certain studies, detailed statistical indicators and significance levels were not fully reported, highlighting the need for further research.

All the reviewed studies employed survey-based methods to assess students' or graduates' soft skills. Key skills emphasized included communication, leadership, creativity, critical thinking, decision-making, emotional intelligence, and adaptability. These studies indicate that soft skills have a positive impact on employability, professional confidence, and success in the labor market.

Evaluation of the impact of soft skills on academic achievement and career success

Our study involved 80 graduates from higher education institutions in Kazakhstan. Data were collected using a specially designed questionnaire based on a 10-point Likert scale (1 – very low, 10 – very high). The questionnaire covered the following five core soft skill components:

- communication;
- teamwork;
- creativity;
- critical thinking;
- emotional intelligence.

In addition, the survey gathered information on graduates' GPA (academic achievement), level of social adaptation, employment status, and personal income (Figure 1). Employment and income data were supplemented with additional information obtained from both graduates and their employers.

The collected data were analyzed using two main statistical methods:

- Pearson and Spearman correlation – to identify relationships between soft skill components and academic performance, social adaptation, and income indicators;
- Linear regression – to assess the extent to which soft skills influence social adaptation and career success.

		Communication	Teamwork	Creativity	Critical_Thinking	Emotional_Intelligence	GPA	Social_Adaptation	Employment_Status	Incom
Communication	Пирсон r	—								
	df	—								
	p- мәні	—								
Teamwork	Пирсон r	0.113	—							
	df	78	—							
	p- мәні	0.319	—							
Creativity	Пирсон r	-0.086	-0.005	—						
	df	78	78	—						
	p- мәні	0.446	0.962	—						
Critical_Thinking	Пирсон r	-0.027	0.035	-0.094	—					
	df	78	78	78	—					
	p- мәні	0.815	0.759	0.406	—					
Emotional_Intelligence	Пирсон r	-0.090	0.006	-0.015	0.085	—				
	df	78	78	78	78	—				
	p- мәні	0.427	0.960	0.898	0.453	—				
GPA	Пирсон r	0.026	-0.062	-0.127	0.072	0.067	—			
	df	78	78	78	78	78	—			
	p- мәні	0.822	0.584	0.261	0.527	0.555	—			
Social_Adaptation	Пирсон r	-0.017	-0.105	0.046	0.124	0.046	0.015	—		
	df	78	78	78	78	78	78	—		
	p- мәні	0.883	0.355	0.683	0.273	0.686	0.898	—		
Employment_Status	Пирсон r	-0.060	-0.096	-0.065	-0.066	-0.153	-0.259	0.156	—	
	df	78	78	78	78	78	78	78	—	
	p- мәні	0.598	0.395	0.565	0.561	0.177	0.021	0.166	—	
Income	Пирсон r	-0.114	-0.183	-0.065	0.137	-0.122	-0.168	0.146	0.706	—
	df	78	78	78	78	78	78	78	78	—
	p- мәні	0.312	0.104	0.566	0.225	0.281	0.135	0.195	< .001	—

Figure 1. Pearson's Correlation Matrix of Soft Skills, GPA, and Career Outcomes

The correlation analysis results provide a comprehensive overview of the relationships between the soft skills of 80 graduates (communication, teamwork, creativity, critical thinking, and emotional intelligence), academic performance (GPA), social adaptation, employment status, and income level. Based on the study data, Pearson's correlation coefficients made it possible to assess both the direction and strength of associations between the variables.

The analysis revealed that the interrelationships among the soft skill components were weak and statistically insignificant. For example, the correlation between communication and teamwork was positive (r =

0.113), but not statistically significant (p = 0.319). Similarly, the associations between creativity, critical thinking, and emotional intelligence were very low and did not allow for reliable interpretation (p > 0.05). These findings suggest that each soft skill develops independently, and a high level in one skill does not automatically ensure a high level in another.

The correlations between GPA and soft skills were also weak. For instance, GPA showed very low correlations with communication (r = 0.026), teamwork (r = -0.062), creativity (r = -0.127), critical thinking (r = 0.072), and emotional intelligence (r = 0.067), with all p-values above 0.05. This indicates that academic

achievement does not directly influence individual soft skill levels and that the development of soft skills largely depends on factors outside academic performance. Social adaptation also demonstrated low correlations with both soft skills and GPA (all $p > 0.27$), suggesting that social adaptation is more strongly linked to personal qualities such as life experience, psychological resilience, and the ability to adjust to the surrounding environment.

One of the most noteworthy findings concerns the role of employment status. A negative but weak correlation was found between GPA and employment status ($r = -0.259$, $p = 0.021$), indicating that in some cases, graduates with relatively lower academic performance may adapt more quickly to the labor market, find employment sooner, and take advantage of career growth opportunities. Although employment status showed a positive association with social adaptation, this relationship was not statistically significant ($r = 0.156$, $p = 0.166$). The strongest and statistically significant pre-

dictor of income level was employment status. The correlation coefficient reached $r = 0.706$ ($p < 0.001$), confirming that graduates with stable employment have significantly higher earnings. Additionally, income level was positively associated with critical thinking ($r = 0.137$, $p = 0.225$) and social adaptation ($r = 0.146$, $p = 0.195$), though these associations were not statistically significant.

Overall, these results indicate that achieving career success depends not only on academic knowledge or individual skills but also on the ability to enter the labor market, secure stable employment, and adapt professionally. Critical thinking may indirectly contribute to income, while the combined influence of soft skills—when aligned with other factors such as social adaptation, motivation, and professional experience—can enhance career outcomes.

Linear regression – used to assess the extent to which soft skills influence social adaptation and career success (Table 3; Table 4).

Table 3.

Goodness-of-fit indicators of the linear regression model assessing the impact of soft skills on social adaptation and career success.

Sample compliance indicators		
Model	R	R ²
1	0.742	0.551

Table 4.

The influence of predictor variables in linear regression on social adaptation and career success.

Predictor Variable	Estimate (B)	SE	t-value	p-value
Constant	29,392.6	156,726	0.1875	0.852
Communication	-5,604.5	7,742	-0.7239	0.471
Teamwork	-10,010.0	7,000	-1.4301	0.157
Creativity	-882.0	7,652	-0.1153	0.909
Critical Thinking	16,817.0	7,275	2.3116	0.024 *
Emotional Intelligence	-3,189.6	7,139	-0.4468	0.656
Social Adaptation	51.1	1,200	0.0426	0.966
Employment Status	215,582.3	26,621	8.0982	< .001 **
GPA	-1,382.9	17,370	-0.0796	0.937

The linear regression analysis, aimed at predicting income level, demonstrated that the constructed model possessed a satisfactory explanatory capacity ($R = 0.742$, $R^2 = 0.551$). This indicates that approximately 55.1% of the variance in income level can be explained by the set of predictor variables included in the model, representing a considerable proportion when assessing the influence of socio-economic factors and personal skills on career success.

The analysis of model coefficients revealed that two variables had a statistically significant effect on income level. First, employment status ($\beta = 215,582.3$, $p < .001$) emerged as the strongest predictor of income, indicating that graduates with stable employment earned substantially higher incomes compared to those unemployed or in temporary positions. Second, critical thinking ($\beta = 16,817.0$, $p = 0.024$) was also identified as a significant positive contributor to income level. Graduates with higher levels of this skill demonstrated increased competitiveness in the labor market, which translated into higher earnings.

The remaining variables—communication ($p = 0.471$), teamwork ($p = 0.157$), creativity ($p = 0.909$), emotional intelligence ($p = 0.656$), social adaptation ($p = 0.966$), and GPA ($p = 0.937$)—did not show a direct statistically significant effect on income. Nevertheless, their combined effect contributed to the model's overall explanatory power, underscoring the importance of the interconnected and cumulative influence of soft skills.

These findings highlight that increasing graduates' income levels requires not only the development of academic knowledge and technical competencies but also ensuring stable employment and enhancing critical thinking abilities. This suggests that higher education programs should be adapted to labor market demands by integrating modules that foster analytical and strategic thinking skills.

Discussion

This study aimed to comprehensively evaluate the influence of soft skills on academic performance, social adaptation, and career success. Our findings are consistent with several international studies. Herlina and

Syahchari, in their assessment of Generation Z students' soft skills, reported that the relationship with academic achievement is neither uniform nor consistent [28]. They emphasized the need for skill development programs in higher education institutions—an observation that aligns with the variability in soft skills levels among students in our sample.

Utomo and colleagues examined the relationship between extracurricular engagement and GPA, finding it to be weak [29]. This parallels our results, where social adaptation demonstrated low correlation with GPA ($p > 0.27$).

Employment status emerged as one of the primary determinants of career success, consistent with Almutairi and Hasanat's conclusion that GPA is not the sole determinant in securing employment, and that a combination of professional adaptability and soft skills is essential [30]. Similarly, Mohammed et al. emphasized that hiring processes for teachers should not rely solely on academic metrics but should also consider adaptability to the labor market and professional experience [31].

Our regression analysis indicated that the most influential predictors of income level were employment status ($\beta = 215,582.3$, $p < 0.001$) and critical thinking ($\beta = 16,817.0$, $p = 0.024$). These results are consistent with Khuan, Koh, and Lin's findings on the impact of emotional intelligence and cognitive abilities on both academic performance and professional success [32].

Additionally, Ramankulov et al. highlighted that fostering creativity can improve graduates' social adaptation and competitiveness in the labor market [33], indirectly supporting our conclusion regarding the cumulative contribution of skills to income prediction. Furthermore, Bora and Baruah [34] stressed that GPA alone is insufficient to predict career success, underlining the importance of targeted soft skills and professional experience development—a point that fully aligns with our findings.

Overall, the results indicate that academic knowledge alone is not enough to ensure career success. Smooth labor market integration, stable employment, and the development of analytical and strategic thinking skills are critical factors. Therefore, incorporating labor market-oriented modules into higher education curricula, designed to enhance critical thinking and professional adaptability, could significantly contribute to graduates' career achievements.

Conclusion

The present study provided a comprehensive analysis of the impact of soft skills on academic achievement, social adaptation, and career success. Data from 80 graduates were examined using Pearson and Spearman correlation analyses, as well as linear regression modeling.

The correlation analysis revealed that the relationships between communication, teamwork, creativity, critical thinking, and emotional intelligence were relatively weak and statistically non-significant ($p > 0.05$). The association between GPA and soft skills was also low—for example, GPA and communication ($r = 0.026$, $p > 0.05$), GPA and teamwork ($r = -0.062$, $p >$

0.05)—indicating that academic performance is not directly influenced by individual soft skills.

Social adaptation also exhibited weak correlations with both soft skills and GPA ($p > 0.27$). However, a strong positive correlation was observed between employment status and income level ($r = 0.706$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that graduates with stable employment earn significantly higher incomes.

The linear regression model explained 55.1% of the variance in income ($R^2 = 0.551$). The most significant predictors were employment status ($\beta = 215,582.3$, $p < 0.001$) and critical thinking ($\beta = 16,817.0$, $p = 0.024$). While other variables (communication, teamwork, creativity, emotional intelligence, social adaptation, GPA) did not exert a direct significant effect on income, their collective contribution enhanced the model's explanatory capacity.

In summary, the findings demonstrate that achieving career success requires more than academic knowledge. Effective labor market integration, stable employment, and the development of critical thinking skills play a decisive role. Therefore, integrating labor market-aligned modules that foster analytical and strategic thinking into higher education programs can enhance graduates' competitiveness and long-term career outcomes.

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